

Article

Evaluating the Reaction Kinetics on the H₂ Reduction of a Manganese Ore at Elevated Temperatures

Authors:

- **Alok Sarkar**, PhD candidate, Norwegian University of Science and Technology
- **Trygve Lindahl Schanche**, SINTEF, Norway
- **Jafar Safarian**, Professor, Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Norwegian University of Science and Technology
- **Maria Wallin**, Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Norwegian University of Science and Technology

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